

FUNCTIONS AND IT'S IMPLICATIONS ON ζ -NANO TOPOLOGICAL SPACE

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ABSTRACT. In this paper, we are studying about a function's between domain ζ -nano topological spaces and codomain nano topological spaces which means every nano topology has its inverse image in ζ -nano topology (i.e., ζ -continuous). We establish the ζ -cluster point in ζ -continuous. We search image from a ζ -open sets (ζ -closed set) to a nano open sets (nano closed sets) is called a ζ -open map (ζ -closed map). Finally, some of the results are portrayed with these ζ -continuity with \mathcal{N} -continuity and we extended to ζ -homeomorphism.

1. INTRODUCTION AND PRELIMINARIES

Thivagar and Richard [4] found the result of Nano-Topology (\mathcal{N}). In this paper, we choose ζ element as one of the elements are $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{R}}$, $\mathcal{U}_{\mathcal{R}}$, and $\mathcal{B}_{\mathcal{R}}$. And compare with all open set containing in the nano topological space and then we get some new open elements which is subcollection of ζ element. From this expansion of nano topology was called ζ -nano topology is developed by Jenavee et al [1, 3] and also investigate with some results related with ζ open and ζ closed sets.

Definition 1.1. [4] Let \mathcal{V} be a non-empty finite set of members are called the universe and \mathcal{R} has an equivalence relation on \mathcal{V} known as the indiscernibility relation. Members belonging to the same equivalence class are called to be indiscernible with each other. The pair $(\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{R})$ is called to be the approximation-space. Let $\mathcal{X} \subset \mathcal{V}$.

- (1) The lower approximation of \mathcal{X} with respect to \mathcal{R} is the set of all members, which can be for certain classified as \mathcal{X} with respect to \mathcal{R} and it is represented by $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X})$. That is,

$$\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}) = \cup_{x \in \mathcal{V}} \{\mathcal{R}(x) : \mathcal{R}(x) \subseteq \mathcal{X}\},$$

where $\mathcal{R}(x)$ denoted the equivalence class determined by x .

- (2) The upper approximation of \mathcal{X} with respect to \mathcal{R} is the set of all members, which can be possibly classified as \mathcal{X} with respect to \mathcal{R} and it is represented by $\mathcal{U}_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X})$.

$$\text{(i.e.)}, \mathcal{U}_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}) = \cup_{x \in \mathcal{V}} \{\mathcal{R}(x) : \mathcal{R}(x) \cap \mathcal{X} \neq \emptyset\}$$

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- (3) The boundary region of \mathcal{X} with respect to \mathcal{R} is the set of all members, which can be neither in nor as not- \mathcal{X} with respect to \mathcal{R} and it is represented by $\mathcal{B}_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X})$.

$$(i.e.), \mathcal{B}_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}) = \mathcal{U}_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}) - \mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}).$$

Definition 1.2. [4] Let \mathcal{V} be the universe \mathcal{R} be an equivalence relation on \mathcal{V} and $\tau_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}) = \{\mathcal{V}, \phi, \mathcal{U}_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}), \mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}), \mathcal{B}_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X})\}$, where $\mathcal{X} \subset \mathcal{V}$. Then $\tau_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X})$ satisfies the following axioms:

- (1) \mathcal{V} and $\phi \in \tau_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X})$.
- (2) The union of the members of any sub-collection of $\tau_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X})$ is in $\tau_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X})$.
- (3) The intersection of the members of finite sub-collection of $\tau_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X})$ is in $\tau_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X})$.

That is, $\tau_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X})$ is a topology on \mathcal{V} is called the Nano topology on \mathcal{V} with respect to \mathcal{X} . $(\mathcal{V}, \tau_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X}))$ is called the Nano topological space. Members of the Nano topology are called Nano open sets in \mathcal{V} . Members of $[\tau_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathcal{X})]^c$ are called Nano closed sets.

Definition 1.3. [1] A subset J of a Nano topological space $(V, \mathcal{N}_{\mathcal{R}})$ is called ζ -Nano-open set if there exists a Nano open set $Z \in \mathcal{N}_{\mathcal{R}}-O$, such that

- (1) $Z \neq \phi, V$.
- (2) $J \subseteq \mathcal{N}_{\mathcal{R}}-int(J) \cup Z$.

In $(V, \mathcal{N}_{\mathcal{R}})$, the member of the open set is said to be ζ -Nano-open and the complement is ζ -Nano-closed set. The collection of all ζ -Nano-open including ϕ, V is said to be ζ -Nano-topological space if satisfies topological space definition. So, this $(V, \mathcal{N}_{\mathcal{R}}, \zeta)$ or $\mathcal{N}-\tau_{\zeta}(J)$ can be rewritten in the form ζ -Nano-topological space on V .

Definition 1.4. [1] Let E be a subset of a ζ -Nano-Topology.

- (1) The union of all Nano- ζ sets contained in E is represent in the form of ζ -Nano-int(E). We can rewrite in the form $\zeta_i(E)$.
- (2) The intersection of all Nano- ζ sets containing in E is represent in the form of ζ -Nano-cl(E). Also we write in the form $\zeta_c(E)$.
- (3) The exterior of ζ -Nano-Topology in E is defined by $\zeta_e(E) = \zeta_i(V - E)$.
- (4) The frontier of ζ -Nano-Topology in E is defined by $\zeta_f(E) = \zeta_c(E) \cap \zeta_c(V - E)$.

Proposition 1.1. [1] In $(V, \mathcal{N}_{\mathcal{R}}, \zeta)$, if E and F are subsets, then the following should be attained.

- (1) $\zeta_{\mathcal{N}-i}(\phi) = \phi$ and $\zeta_{\mathcal{N}-c}(\phi) = \phi$.
- (2) $\zeta_{\mathcal{N}-i}(V) = V$ and $\zeta_{\mathcal{N}-c}(V) = V$.
- (3) $\zeta_{\mathcal{N}-i}(E) \subseteq E \subseteq \zeta_{\mathcal{N}-c}(E)$.
- (4) $E \subseteq F \Rightarrow \zeta_{\mathcal{N}-i}(E) \subseteq \zeta_{\mathcal{N}-i}(F)$ and $\zeta_{\mathcal{N}-c}(E) \subseteq \zeta_{\mathcal{N}-i}(F)$.
- (5) $\zeta_{\mathcal{N}-i}(E \cap F) \subseteq \zeta_{\mathcal{N}-i}(E) \cap \zeta_{\mathcal{N}-i}(F)$.
- (6) $\zeta_{\mathcal{N}-c}(E \cap F) = \zeta_{\mathcal{N}-c}(E) \cap \zeta_{\mathcal{N}-c}(F)$.
- (7) $\zeta_{\mathcal{N}-c}(E \cup F) \supseteq \zeta_{\mathcal{N}-c}(E) \cup \zeta_{\mathcal{N}-c}(F)$.
- (8) $\zeta_{\mathcal{N}-i}(E \cup F) = \zeta_{\mathcal{N}-i}(E) \cup \zeta_{\mathcal{N}-i}(F)$.
- (9) $\zeta_{\mathcal{N}-i}(\zeta_{\mathcal{N}-i}(E)) \subseteq \zeta_{\mathcal{N}-i}(E)$.
- (10) $\zeta_{\mathcal{N}-c}(\zeta_{\mathcal{N}-c}(E)) \supseteq \zeta_{\mathcal{N}-c}(E)$.
- (11) $\zeta_{\mathcal{N}-i}(E) = E = \zeta_{\mathcal{N}-c}(E)$.

Theorem 1.2. [3] In (V, τ_{ζ}) , Z is ζ -closed set iff $Z = \zeta$ -closure set.

Corollary 1.3. [3] In (V, τ_{ζ}) , Z is ζ -open set iff $Z = \zeta$ -interior set.

Lemma 1.4. [3] In (V, τ_{ζ}) , $\zeta_c(S)$ is the smallest ζ -closed set containing S .

The rest of the paper is content are present: In section-2, gives some functions and it's implications like ζ-continuity, ζ-open map, ζ-closed map, ζ-cluster point and ζ-homeomorphism. Few result is based with these content are present. The conclusion of the current study is set forth in section-3.

2. ζ-CONTINUITY

Definition 2.1. Let $(V, \tau_\zeta(Y))$ is ζ-nano topological space and $(W, \tau_{\mathcal{N}}(Z))$ is nano topological space. Then a mapping $f : (V, \tau_\zeta(Y)) \rightarrow (W, \tau_{\mathcal{N}}(Z))$ is ζ-continuous on V, if f^{-1} is a ζ-open set in V for each \mathcal{N} -open set Z in W .

Example 2.2. Let $V = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4\}$ with $V/\mathcal{R} = \{\{v_1, v_3\}, \{v_2\}, \{v_4\}\}$. Then, $Y = \{v_1, v_4\} \subseteq V$. So, $\tau_{\mathcal{N}}(Y) = \{\phi, V, \{v_4\}, \{v_1, v_3, v_4\}, \{v_1, v_3\}\}$. Now, $\zeta_Y = \{v_1, v_3\}$ then $\tau_\zeta(Y) = \{\phi, V, \{v_1\}, \{v_3\}, \{v_4\}, \{v_1, v_3\}, \{v_1, v_4\}, \{v_3, v_4\}, \{v_1, v_3, v_4\}\}$. Let $W = \{w_1, w_2, w_3, w_4\}$ with $W/\mathcal{R} = \{\{w_1, w_3\}, \{w_2\}, \{w_4\}\}$. Then, $Z = \{w_1, w_4\} \subseteq W$. So, $\tau_{\mathcal{N}}(Z) = \{\phi, W, \{w_4\}, \{w_1, w_3, w_4\}, \{w_1, w_3\}\}$.

Define $f : (V, \tau_\zeta(Y)) \rightarrow (W, \tau_{\mathcal{N}}(Z))$ and f are denoted as $f(v_1) = w_1, f(v_2) = w_2, f(v_3) = w_3, f(v_4) = w_4$. Then, $f^{-1}(\{w_4\}) = \{v_4\}, f^{-1}(\{w_1, w_3\}) = \{v_1, v_3\}, f^{-1}(\{w_1, w_3, w_4\}) = \{v_1, v_3, v_4\}$. (i.e) (That is), the inverse image of every ζ-open set in V is \mathcal{N} -open in W. Thence, f is ζ-continuous.

Note:

- (1) In codomain, the collection of all $\tau_{\mathcal{N}}$ open members on W.
- (2) In domain, the collection of all τ_ζ open members on V.
- (3) In domain, the different colour denotes different open sets,
 - (a) red-ζ-nano open sets.
 - (b) green-nano open sets.
 - (c) cyan-mapping between domain and codomain.

Theorem 2.1. Every \mathcal{N} -continuous function is ζ-continuous.

Proof. Let $f : V \rightarrow W$ be a \mathcal{N} -continuous function. If Z is \mathcal{N} -open in W, then $f^{-1}(Z)$ is \mathcal{N} -open in V and by definition 1.3, $f^{-1}(Z)$ is ζ-open in W. So, using definition 2.1, f is ζ-continuous. □

Remark. The converse of the last theorem 2.1 may be false.

Example 2.3. In example 2.2, $f^{-1}(\{w_1, w_4\}) = \{v_1, v_4\}$ is ζ-open but not \mathcal{N} -open.

Definition 2.4. Let V be a space and $Z \subseteq V$. Then, a point $z \in V$ is called a ζ -cluster point of Z if for every ζ -open set U containing z , $U \cap (Z - \{z\}) \neq \phi$.

Proposition 2.2. In $(V, \tau_\zeta(Y))$,

- (1) If Z_i is ζ -closed for each $i \in \mathcal{I}$, then $\bigcap_{i \in \mathcal{I}} Z_i$ is ζ -closed.
- (2) If Z_i is ζ -open for each $i \in \mathcal{I}$, then $\bigcup_{i \in \mathcal{I}} Z_i$ is ζ -open.

Proof. (1) Let that $Z = \bigcap_{i \in \mathcal{I}} Z_i$ and $z \in \zeta_c(Z)$. By definition 2.4, for every ζ -open set O containing z , $Z \cap O \neq \phi \Rightarrow Z_i \cap O \neq \phi$ for each $i \in \mathcal{I}$. If $z \notin Z$, then $z \notin Z_i$ for some $i \in \mathcal{I}$. Since Z_i is ζ -closed, by theorem 1.2, $Z_i = \zeta_c(Z_i)$ and $z \notin \zeta_c(Z_i) \Rightarrow \exists$ a ζ -open set O containing z such that $Z_i \cap O = \phi$. This contradiction gives that $z \in Z$ and $\zeta_c(Z) \subseteq Z$. By using proposition 1.1, it gives $Z = \zeta_c(Z)$. Using theorem 1.2, Z is ζ -closed, (i. e), $\bigcap_{i \in \mathcal{I}} Z_i$. Hence, it proves (1).
 (2) Let Z_i is ζ -open for each $i \in \mathcal{I}$. Then, from the definition 1.3, $V - Z_i$ is ζ -closed for each $i \in \mathcal{I}$. From (i), $\bigcap_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (V - Z_i)$ is ζ -closed $\Rightarrow V - (\bigcup_{i \in \mathcal{I}} Z_i)$ is ζ -closed and $\bigcup_{i \in \mathcal{I}} Z_i$ is ζ -open. Thus, it proves (2). □

Theorem 2.3. A function $f : V \rightarrow W$ is ζ -continuous \Leftrightarrow for each point $v \in V$ and each \mathcal{N} -open set Z in W with $f(v) \in Z$, there is a ζ -open set U in V such that $v \in U$ and $f(U) \subseteq Z$.

Proof. Let f is ζ -continuous. Assume $v \in V$ and Z be \mathcal{N} -open set in W such that $f(v) \in Z$. Then, $v \in f^{-1}(Z)$ and by definition 2.1, $f^{-1}(Z)$ is a ζ -open set in V . Now, take $U = f^{-1}(Z)$. Then, U is ζ -open set in V such that $v \in U$ and $f(U) \subseteq Z$.

\Leftarrow , Assume for each point $v \in V$ and each \mathcal{N} -open set Z in W with $f(v) \in Z$, there is a ζ -open set U in V such that $v \in U$ and $f(U) \subseteq Z$. Let Z be \mathcal{N} -open in W and $v \in f^{-1}(Z)$. Then, $f(v) \in Z$. By our assumption, \exists a ζ -open set U_v in V such that $v \in U_v$ and $f(U_v) \subseteq Z \Rightarrow v \in U_v \subseteq f^{-1}(Z)$ and $f^{-1}(Z) = \bigcup \{U_v : v \in f^{-1}(Z)\}$. Using the proposition 2.2, $f^{-1}(Z)$ is ζ -open in V and then by definition 2.1, f is ζ -continuous. □

Theorem 2.4. Let $f : V \rightarrow W$ is a function. Then, the following are equivalent:

- (1) f is ζ -continuous.
- (2) The inverse image of each closed set in W is ζ -closed in V .
- (3) For each subset Z of V , $f(\zeta_c(Z)) \subseteq \zeta_c(f(Z))$.

Proof. Case (1): (1) \Rightarrow (2). Assume f is ζ -continuous. Let P be a \mathcal{N} -closed subset of W . Then, $W - P$ is \mathcal{N} -open in W . And by definition 2.1, $f^{-1}(W - P)$ is ζ -open in $V \Rightarrow V - f^{-1}(P)$ is ζ -open in V and $f^{-1}(P)$ is ζ -closed in V . Hence, it proves.

Case (2): (2) \Rightarrow (3). Assume the inverse image of every closed set in W is ζ -closed in V . Let $Z \subseteq V$ Then, $f(Z) \subseteq \mathcal{N}_c(f(Z)) \Rightarrow f^{-1}(f(Z)) \subseteq f^{-1}(\mathcal{N}_c(f(Z))) \Rightarrow Z \subseteq f^{-1}(\mathcal{N}_c(f(Z)))$. Here, $\mathcal{N}_c(f(Z))$ is a closed set in W and $f^{-1}(\mathcal{N}_c(f(Z)))$ is ζ -closed in V containing Z , by our assumption. By lemma 1.4, $Z \subseteq \zeta_c(Z) \subseteq f^{-1}(\mathcal{N}_c(f(Z))) \Rightarrow f(\zeta_c(Z)) \subseteq (f(f^{-1}(\mathcal{N}_c(f(Z)))) \subseteq \mathcal{N}_c(f(Z))$. Thus, it proves.

Case (3): (3) \Rightarrow (1). Assume that for each subset Z of V , $f(\zeta_c(Z)) \subseteq \mathcal{N}_c(f(Z))$. Let P be a \mathcal{N} closed subset of W . Then, $f^{-1}(P) \subseteq V$. Since, we have $f(\zeta_c(f^{-1}(P))) \subseteq \mathcal{N}_c(f(f^{-1}(P))) \subseteq \mathcal{N}_c(P) = P \Rightarrow \zeta_c(f^{-1}(P)) \subseteq f^{-1}(P)$. By theorem 1.1, $f^{-1}(P) \subseteq \zeta_c(f^{-1}(P))$. Then, $f^{-1}(P) = \zeta_c(f^{-1}(P))$. It gives, $f^{-1}(P)$ is ζ -closed in V . If Q is \mathcal{N} -open in W , then $W - Q$ is \mathcal{N} -closed in W . Since, $f^{-1}(W - Q)$ is ζ -closed in $V \Rightarrow V - f^{-1}(Q)$

ζ-closed in V and $f^{-1}(Q)$ is ζ-open in V. From definition 2.1, f is ζ-continuous. Thence, it proves. \square

Corollary 2.5. A function $f : V \rightarrow W$ is ζ-continuous \Leftrightarrow for each subset P of W, $\zeta_c(f^{-1}(P)) \subseteq f^{-1}(\zeta_c(P))$.

Proof. Let f is ζ-continuous and $P \subseteq W$. Then, $f^{-1}(P) \subseteq V$. From the theorem 2.4, $f(\zeta_c(f^{-1}(P))) \subseteq \mathcal{N}_c(f(f^{-1}(P))) \subseteq \mathcal{N}_c(P)$ and $\zeta_c(f^{-1}(P)) \subseteq f^{-1}(\mathcal{N}_c(P))$.

\Leftarrow (Conversely), let for each subset P of W, $\zeta_c(f^{-1}(P)) \subseteq f^{-1}(\mathcal{N}_c(P))$ and P be \mathcal{N} -open in W. Since, $\zeta_c(f^{-1}(P)) \subseteq f^{-1}(\mathcal{N}_c(P)) \Rightarrow f(\zeta_c(f^{-1}(P))) \subseteq f(f^{-1}(\mathcal{N}_c(P))) \subseteq \mathcal{N}_c(P)$. If $P = f(Z)$ where $Z \subseteq V$, then $f(\zeta_c(P)) \subseteq \mathcal{N}_c(f(Z))$ and by theorem 2.4, f is ζ-continuous. \square

Definition 2.5. A function $f : V \rightarrow W$ is said to be ζ-open map if the image of each open set in V is a ζ-open set in W.

We can rewrite ζ-open map as ζ-open.

Proposition 2.6. Every \mathcal{N} open map is ζ-open.

Proof. Let V is \mathcal{N} open. Since, \exists nano open O such that $O = \mathcal{N}_i$. From the definition 1.3, Therefore, V is ζ-open. \square

Remark. The converse of the before theorem 2.6 can be false.

Example 2.6. Let $V = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4\}$ with $V/\mathcal{R} = \{\{v_1, v_3\}, \{v_2\}, \{v_4\}\}$. Then, $Y = \{v_1, v_4\} \subseteq V$. So, $\tau_{\mathcal{N}}(Y) = \{\phi, V, \{v_4\}, \{v_1, v_3, v_4\}, \{v_1, v_3\}\}$. Now, $\zeta_Y = \{v_1, v_3\}$ then $\tau_{\zeta}(Y) = \{\phi, V, \{v_1\}, \{v_3\}, \{v_4\}, \{v_1, v_3\}, \{v_1, v_4\}, \{v_3, v_4\}, \{v_1, v_3, v_4\}\}$. Define $f : (V, \tau_{\mathcal{N}}(Y)) \rightarrow (V, \tau_{\zeta}(Y))$ and f are denoted as $f(v_1) = w_1, f(v_2) = w_2, f(v_3) = w_3, f(v_4) = w_4, f(\{v_3, v_4\}) = \{v_3, v_4\}$ is ζ-open but not \mathcal{N} open.

Theorem 2.7. A function $f : V \rightarrow W$ is ζ-open \Leftrightarrow for any subset P of W and any closed subset Q of V containing $f^{-1}(P)$, \exists a ζ-closed set R of W containing P such that $f^{-1}(R) \subseteq Q$.

Proof. Let f is ζ-open, $P \subseteq W$ and Q be a closed subset of V such that $f^{-1}(P) \subseteq Q$. So, $V-Q$ is \mathcal{N} -open in V. Since, f is ζ-open, by definition 2.5, $f(V - Q)$ is ζ-open in W $\Rightarrow W - f(V - Q)$ is ζ-closed in W. Since $f^{-1}(P) \subseteq Q, V - Q \subseteq V - f^{-1}(P) = f^{-1}(W - P) \Rightarrow f(V - Q) \subseteq f(f^{-1}(W - P)) \subseteq W - P$. So $P \subseteq W - f(V - Q)$. Then, $f^{-1}(W - f(V - Q)) = V - f^{-1}(f(V - Q)) \subseteq Q$. Hence, $R = W - f(V - Q)$ is ζ-closed set of W containing P and $f^{-1}(R) \subseteq Q$.

\Leftarrow , let reverse part is holds. Let U be \mathcal{N} -open in V. Then $V-U$ is \mathcal{N} -closed in V and $f^{-1}(W - f(U)) \subseteq V - U$. Since, \exists a ζ-closed set R of W such that $W - f(U) \subseteq R$ and $f^{-1}(R) \subseteq V - U$. Therefore, $W - f(U) \subseteq R \Rightarrow W - R \subseteq f(U)$. And $f^{-1}(R) \subseteq V - U \Rightarrow U \subseteq V - f^{-1}(R) = f^{-1}(W - R) \Rightarrow f(U) \subseteq f(f^{-1}(W - R)) \subseteq W - R$. This gives, $f(U) = W - R$ and $f(U)$ is ζ-open in W. Thus, f is ζ-open. \square

Theorem 2.8. If $f : V \rightarrow W$ is ζ-open, then $f(\mathcal{N}_i(Z)) \subseteq \zeta_i(f(Z))$ for every subset Z of V.

Proof. Suppose $f : V \rightarrow W$ is ζ-open and $Z \subseteq V$. Since, $\mathcal{N}_i(Z)$ is \mathcal{N} -open in V, by definition 2.5, $f(\mathcal{N}(Z))$ is ζ-open in W and by corollary 1.3, then $f(\mathcal{N}_i(Z)) = \zeta_i(f(\mathcal{N}_i(Z)))$. So, $f(\mathcal{N}(Z)) \subseteq f(Z)$. By proposition 1.1(4), $\zeta_i(f(\mathcal{N}_i(Z))) \subseteq \zeta_i(f(Z))$ and $f(\mathcal{N}(Z)) \subseteq \zeta_i(f(Z))$. \square

Theorem 2.9. *If $f : V \rightarrow W$ is ζ -open, then $f^{-1}(\zeta_c(P)) \subseteq \mathcal{N}_c(f^{-1}(P))$ for every subset P of W .*

Proof. Let $f : V \rightarrow W$ is ζ -open and $P \subseteq Y$. Then, $f^{-1}(P) \subseteq \mathcal{N}_c(f^{-1}(P))$ and $\mathcal{N}_c(f^{-1}(P))$ is closed in V . By theorem 2.7, \exists a ζ -closed set Q of W containing P such that $f^{-1}(Q) \subseteq \mathcal{N}_c(f^{-1}(P))$. Since, $P \subseteq Q$, by proposition 2.2 and theorem 1.2, $\zeta_c(P) \subseteq \zeta_c(Q) = Q$. So, $f^{-1}(\zeta_c(P)) \subseteq f^{-1}(Q) \subseteq \mathcal{N}_c(f^{-1}(P))$. \square

Definition 2.7. A function $f : V \rightarrow W$ is said to be ζ -closed map if the image of each closed set in V is a ζ -closed set in W . We rewrite ζ -closed map as ζ -closed.

Theorem 2.10. *Every \mathcal{N} closed map is ζ -closed.*

Proof. Let V is \mathcal{N} closed. Since, \exists nano closed C such that $C = \mathcal{N}_c$. From the definition 1.3, Therefore, V is ζ -closed. \square

Remark. *The converse of the before theorem 2.10 can be false.*

Example 2.8. In example 2.6, $f(\{v_2, v_3\}) = \{v_2, v_3\}$ is ζ -closed but not \mathcal{N} -closed.

Theorem 2.11. *A function $f : V \rightarrow W$ is ζ -closed \Leftrightarrow for each subset P of W and each open set Q in V containing $f^{-1}(P)$, \exists a ζ -open set O of W containing P such that $f^{-1}(O) \subseteq Q$.*

Proof. Let f is ζ -closed and $P \subseteq W$ and Q be an open set of V such that $f^{-1}(P) \subseteq Q$. Then, $V - Q$ is closed in V . Since, f is ζ -closed, by definition 2.7, $f(V - Q)$ is ζ -closed in W . We take $O = W - f(V - Q)$. Then O is ζ -open in W . Again since, $f^{-1}(P) \subseteq Q$, then $P \subseteq O$ and $f^{-1}(O) = f^{-1}(W - f(V - Q)) = V - f^{-1}(f(V - Q)) \subseteq Q$.

\Leftarrow , let for each subset P of W and each open set Q in V containing $f^{-1}(P)$, \exists a ζ -open set O of W containing P such that $f^{-1}(O) \subseteq Q$ and G be a closed set of V . Then, $V - G$ is open in V and $f^{-1}(W - f(G)) \subseteq V - G$. By our assumption, \exists a ζ -open set O of W such that $W - f(G) \subseteq O$ and $f^{-1}(O) \subseteq V - G$. So, $G \subseteq V - f^{-1}(O)$. Then, $W - O \subseteq f(G) \subseteq f(V - f^{-1}(O)) = f(f^{-1}(W - O)) \subseteq W - O \Rightarrow f(G) = W - O$. And $f(G)$ is ζ -closed in W . This gives f is ζ -closed. \square

Theorem 2.12. *If $f : V \rightarrow W$ is ζ -closed, then $\zeta_c(f(Z)) \subseteq f(\mathcal{N}_c(Z))$ for every subset Z of V .*

Proof. Let $f : V \rightarrow W$ is ζ -closed and $Z \subseteq V$. Then, $\mathcal{N}_c(Z)$ is closed in V . By definition 2.7, $f(\mathcal{N}_c(Z))$ is ζ -closed in W . By theorem 1.2(4), $\zeta_c(f(\mathcal{N}_c(Z))) = f(\mathcal{N}_c(Z))$. Since, $f(Z) \subseteq f(\mathcal{N}_c(Z))$, by proposition 1.1(4), $\zeta_c(f(Z)) \subseteq \zeta_c(f(\mathcal{N}_c(Z))) = f(\mathcal{N}_c(Z))$. \square

Theorem 2.13. *For each bijective function $f : V \rightarrow W$, the following are equivalent :*

- (1) $f^{-1} : W \rightarrow V$ is ζ -continuous.
- (2) f is ζ -open.
- (3) f is ζ -closed.

Proof. Case(1): Let f^{-1} is ζ -continuous. If O is open in V , then by definition 2.1, $(f^{-1})^{-1}(O) = f(O)$ is ζ -open in W . So, f is ζ -open. Hence, (1) \Rightarrow (2).

Case(2): Assume f is ζ -open. If C is \mathcal{N} -closed set of V , then $V - C$ is \mathcal{N} -open in V . From definition 2.5, $f(V - C) = W - f(C)$ is ζ -open in W and so $f(C)$ is ζ -closed in W . Thus, (2) \Rightarrow (3).

Case(3): Suppose f is ζ -closed. If C is a \mathcal{N} -closed set of V , then by definition 2.7, $f(C)$ is ζ -closed in W . So, $(f^{-1})^{-1}(C)$ is ζ -closed in W . By theorem 2.4, f^{-1} is ζ -continuous. Hence, (3) \Rightarrow (1). \square

Definition 2.9. A bijection $f : V \rightarrow W$ is said to be ζ -homeomorphism if both f and f^{-1} are ζ -continuous.

Theorem 2.14. Every \mathcal{N} -homeomorphism is a ζ -homeomorphism.

Proof. Suppose, if $f : V \rightarrow W$ is a \mathcal{N} -homeomorphism, then f is bijective and both f and f^{-1} are \mathcal{N} -continuous. From the theorem 2.1, f and f^{-1} are ζ -continuous. So, by definition 2.9, f is a ζ -homeomorphism. \square

Remark. The converse before theorem 2.14 can be false.

Example 2.10. In example 2.6, $f(\{v_3, v_4\}) = \{v_3, v_4\}$ is ζ -homeomorphism but not \mathcal{N} -homeomorphism because it is not both f and f^{-1} are ζ -continuous.

Theorem 2.15. Let $f : V \rightarrow W$ be a bijective ζ -continuous function. Then, the following are equivalent :

- (1) f is ζ -open.
- (2) f is ζ -homeomorphism.
- (3) f is ζ -closed.

Proof. Case (1): Assume (1) holds. If O is open in V , then by definition 2.5, $f(O)$ is ζ -open in W . But, $f(O) = (f^{-1})^{-1}(O)$. So, $(f^{-1})^{-1}(O)$ is ζ -open in W . From the definition 2.1, f^{-1} is ζ -continuous. Thus, (2) is proved.

Case (2): Assume (2) holds. Let C be closed in V . Then, by definition 7.1, f^{-1} is ζ -continuous. And by theorem 2.4, $(f^{-1})^{-1}(C) = f(C)$ is ζ -closed in W . By definition 1.4, f is ζ -closed. Thus, (3) is proved.

Case (3): Assume (3) holds. If O is open in V , then $V-O$ is closed in V . By definition 2.7, $f(V-O)$ is ζ -closed in W . But $f(V-O) = W - f(O) \Rightarrow W - f(O)$ is ζ -closed in W and so $f(O)$ is ζ -open in W . From the definition 1.1, f is ζ -open. Thus, (1) is proved. \square

3. CONCLUSION

This paper, we learned the concept of functions like ζ -continuity, ζ -open map, ζ -closed map, ζ -cluster point and ζ -homeomorphism. In the future, we can study in the area of irresolute functions (i.e., the domain and the codomain are the ζ -nano topological spaces) and as well as ζ -open map, ζ -closed map. We can extend by finding an inverse image or image for the ζ closed set to ζ closed set also. And we can learn in various areas of topological spaces with associated applications.

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REFERENCES

- [1] K. S. Jenavee, R. Asokan, and O. Nethaji. ζ -open sets in nano topological space, Indian journal of natural sciences, 13(74) (2022), 49015-49020.
- [2] K. S. Jenavee, R. Asokan, and O. Nethaji. A Note on ζ -nano topological space, (Communicated).
- [3] K. S. Jenavee, R. Asokan, and O. Nethaji. New separation axioms in ζ -nano topological space, Turkish journal of computer and mathematical education, 13(3) 2022, 133-139.
- [4] M. Lellis Thivagar, and Carmel Richard. On Nano Forms of Weakly open sets, International Journal of Mathematics and Statistics Invention, 1(1) (2013), 31-37.
- [5] Lynn Arthur Steen, and J. Arthur Seebach. Counterexamples in topology, Dover Publications, (1995).
- [6] Z. Pawalk, Rough Sets, International Journal of Computer and Information Science, 11 (5)(1982), 341-356..
- [7] Z. Pawalk, Rough Sets: Theoretical Aspects of Reasoning About Data, Kluwer Academic Publishers, Boston, (1991).

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